

The Deuterium Isotope Effect on the Pfeiffer Effect in Optically Labile Coordination Compounds

STANLEY KIRSCHNER and JOANNE GABAY

Department of Chemistry, Wayne State University, Detroit, Michigan 48202, U.S.A.

THE Pfeiffer Effect¹ is the change in optical rotation of an optically active system (usually a solution of one enantiomer of an optically active compound, called the "environment substance"), upon the addition of a racemic mixture of a dissymmetric, optically labile coordination compound. Considerable work has been done on this effect by Brasted, Yoneda, Brittain, Kirschner and others²⁻¹¹, and several proposed mechanisms to explain it have been described in an excellent review by Schipper¹².

The Pfeiffer effect has been utilized for the study of the resolution and racemization of optically active coordination compounds¹³ and for studies of the optical properties of complexes which are extremely labile and which racemize very rapidly¹⁴. Recent work^{15,16} has also been done on applying the Pfeiffer effect to the determination of absolute configurations of optically active complexes which are also optically labile and organic compounds and on explaining the nature of the "equilibrium displacement" mechanism proposed for the effect. In this paper further work is described on the nature and mechanism of the Pfeiffer effect and on the utilization of the deuterium isotope effect to assist in the elucidation of the mechanism.

The equilibrium displacement mechanism for the Pfeiffer effect:

It has been proposed by Dwyer *et al.*³ that an equilibrium exists between the enantiomers of a racemic mixture of an optically labile, dissymmetric complex in solution, with the equilibrium constant being equal to unity. However, in the presence of an appropriate optically active environment substance (one which will cause the Pfeiffer effect to occur and which will not displace a coordinated ligand during the time required for the appearance of the Pfeiffer effect), this equilibrium is shifted toward one of the enantiomers, with the equilibrium constant becoming greater or less than 1, depending on the direction of the shift.

If such a shift occurs, it should be possible to identify the enantiomer produced in excess by means of techniques such as optical rotatory dispersion and circular dichroism, as well as by a "time" experiment (see below). For example, Fig. 1 shows the circular dichroism spectrum of (+)- $D[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_3]^{3-}$ in water along with the Pfeiffer circular dichroism spectrum of $D,L-[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_3]^{3-}$ in water containing *d*-cinchonine hydrochloride as the environment substance ('ox = oxalate anion). It can be seen that the two spectra are essentially the same, the difference in intensity

between them being due to the different concentrations of the optically active complex ion in solution in the two cases.

Fig. 1. (A) Circular dichroism spectrum of (+)- $D[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_3]^{3-}$ in H_2O . (B) Pfeiffer circular dichroism spectrum of $D,L-[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_3]^{3-}$ in water containing *d*-cinchonine hydrochloride (all measurements at 23°).

The "time" experiment referred to above is described in Fig. 2. In this figure it can be seen that the optical rotation of *levo*-malic acid does not change with time. However, when $D,L-[\text{Ni}(\text{o-phen})_2]^{2+}$ is added to the solution (at time=0),

Fig. 2. The "time" experiment. The Pfeiffer effect and subsequent racemization in water of $D,L-[\text{Ni}(\text{o-phen})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ with *levo*-malic acid as the environment substance. (A) *Levo*-malic acid in water; (B) *Levo*-malic acid + $D,L-[\text{Ni}(\text{o-phen})_2]\text{Cl}_2$; (C) the system in (B) + added *dextro*-malic acid after 123 hr; (D) Racemization of the system in (C) (of the excess $L-[\text{Ni}(\text{o-phen})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ produced via the Pfeiffer effect).

the Pfeiffer effect develops, with its maximum being attained at about 120 hr (*o-phen* = *ortho*-phenanthroline). If, at that time, exactly the same concentration of *d*-malic acid is added to the system, then this has the effect of eliminating or "optically neutralizing" the optically active environment, with the result that the excess of the *levo* enantiomer of

the complex undergoes racemization until the optical rotation of the substance disappears. Note however that the nickel-*ortho*-phenanthroline complex retains its integrity throughout the Pfeiffer effect experiment, as evidenced by the fact that there is no change in the uv-visible spectrum of the complex throughout the entire "time" experiment. All this provides considerable support for the mechanism which proposes that one enantiomer of the complex is produced in excess during the appearance of the Pfeiffer effect.

It should be noted that, in Fig. 2, if the *d*-malic acid had not been added, then curve B would continue parallel to the horizontal axis until decomposition begins. This permits the study of many optical properties of extremely labile complexes which heretofore could not be studied because the racemization rate is so rapid that any resolved compounds would racemize too quickly to be studied. With the displaced equilibrium mentioned above continuing for some time, the excess of one enantiomer can be studied with regard to racemization rate, optical rotatory dispersion, circular dichroism, etc. This has already been achieved with certain very optically labile complexes¹⁴.

A proposed explanation for the displacement of the equilibrium between the complex enantiomers, which is postulated to occur during the Pfeiffer effect, is that hydrogen bonding occurs preferentially between electronegative atoms of an environment substance of a given absolute configuration and the π -electron clouds of the ligands of one enantiomer of the complex¹⁵. Such hydrogen bonding interactions to π -electron clouds of aromatic and unsaturated systems are known to occur with organic molecules^{17,18}.

This proposal is a most attractive one from several standpoints. First of all it provides an explanation for the chiral discrimination which is observed to occur for the Pfeiffer effect, since molecular models of the proposed system indicate that *S*-malic acid, for example, fits quite well into the Δ_{e_s} propeller system of the $[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})_3]^{2+}$ enantiomer with no strong non-bonded hydrogen interactions, whereas the *R* enantiomer of malic acid in the same propeller system shows two strong non-bonded hydrogen interactions. Consequently, the Δ_{e_s} configuration is stabilized by *S*-malic acid, resulting in an equilibrium shift in favour of the Δ_{e_s} enantiomer.

Also, the initially unexpected behaviour of Pfeiffer-active systems with pH changes is explained well by this proposal. One might expect that with increasing pH, Pfeiffer activity would increase, since chiral recognition by an optically active complex cation of an anionic environment substance (e.g., *levo*-malate ion) would be expected to be greater than that for the same complex cation and a neutral environment substance (e.g., *levo*-malic acid). In fact, the opposite behaviour is observed, with the Pfeiffer activity undergoing a marked decrease with an increase in pH. This can be explained by the

hydrogen bonding proposal, since an increase in pH will result in removal of the carboxylic hydrogens, thus diminishing the ability of the proposed hydrogen bonding to occur¹⁵.

The Deuterium isotope effect on the Pfeiffer effect:

If the hydrogen-bonding mechanism proposed above has validity, it should be possible to observe a deuterium isotope effect in the system which utilizes *S*-malic acid as an environment substance, since, in D_2O , the hydrogens of malic acid capable of undergoing hydrogen bonding would be exchanged for deuterium. The effects of "deuterium bonding" compared to hydrogen bonding should be observable in at least two ways—(a) an expected decrease in the rate of appearance of the Pfeiffer effect due to a slower "deuterium bonding" effects, and (b) a diminution in the magnitude of the Pfeiffer effect because of the lesser ability of "deuterium bonding" to occur (compared to hydrogen bonding) because of weaker electrostatic interactions.

Consequently, the entire Pfeiffer effect experiment utilizing $D,L\text{-}[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})_3]^{2+}$ and *S*-(-)-*D*-malic acid was performed using D_2O as a solvent in place of water. Fig. 3 shows the results of this experiment. Curve B is the Pfeiffer effect for the system in water. Curve A is that for the system in D_2O . It can be seen from Fig. 3 that the rate of appearance of the effect in D_2O is significantly less than that observed in H_2O . It can also be seen that the magnitude of the effect in D_2O is considerably less than in H_2O —both results being in accord with what would be expected if hydrogen bonding plays a significant role in the Pfeiffer effect.

Fig. 3. The deuterium isotope effect on the Pfeiffer effect. (A) $D,L\text{-}[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ (0.05 M) + *levo*-malic acid (0.05 M) in D_2O ; (B) $D,L\text{-}[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ (0.05 M) + *levo*-malic acid (0.05 M) in H_2O ; (C) *levo*-malic acid (0.05 M) in H_2O .

Experimental

ORD and CD spectra were determined on a Cary-60 spectropolarimeter using a CD attachment for the CD spectra. Optical rotations at single wavelengths were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 141

photoelectric polarimeter. The designations "R" and "S" refer to the absolute configurations of organic compounds using the system developed by Cahn, Prelog and Ingold^{19,20}. The optically active organic compounds used as environment substances were purchased in the purest forms available and their optical rotations were checked against the literature values. The *D,L*-[Ni(*o*-phen)₂]Cl₂ complex was synthesized according to the method of Kauffman and Takahashi²¹. The D₂O was purchased as reagent grade material in greater than 99% purity. The Pfeiffer effect studies were carried out at room temperature in solutions in which the concentrations of the complex and environment substance were 0.02 *M* and 0.04 *M*, respectively (Fig. 2), and 0.05 *M* in each (Fig. 3).

Conclusions :

Evidence is presented herewith in support of a generalized "equilibrium displacement" mechanism for the Pfeiffer effect and for the "hydrogen bonding" mechanism to explain this proposed equilibrium displacement. In particular, the deuterium isotope effect on the Pfeiffer effect occurs in a manner consistent with the proposed hydrogen bonding between labile protons (or deuterons) of the environment substance and the π -electron clouds of the ligands of optically labile, racemic complexes, thus modifying their ability to undergo configurational changes and resulting in an equilibrium displacement between the enantiomers of the complex.

References

1. P. PFEIFFER and K. QUEHL, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 2667; 1932, 65, 560.
2. F. P. DWYER, E. G. GYARFAS and M. F. O'DWYER, *Nature (London)*, 1951, 167, 1036; *J. Proc. R. Soc. N. S. Wales*, 1955, 89, 146.
3. S. KIRSCHNER and N. AHMAD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 1910; *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 14, 215; R. J. POLLOCK, S. KIRSCHNER and S. POLICEC, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 16, 522.
4. S. KIRSCHNER and N. AHMAD, in S. KIRSCHNER (Ed.), "Coordination Chemistry, Proc. JOHN C. BAILAR, Jr. Symp.," Plenum Press, New York, 1969.
5. E. C. GYARFAS, *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1954, 4, 73; J. D. GUNTER and A. F. SCHREINER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 15, 117.
6. S. KIRSCHNER and N. AHMAD, in M. CAIS (Ed.), "Progress in Coordination Chemistry", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968; *Rec. Chem. Progr.*, 1971, 32, 29; N. AHMAD, Ph.D. Dissertation, Wayne State University, 1969.
7. E. E. TURNER and M. M. HARRIS, *Q. Rev. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1, 299.
8. R. C. BRASTED, T. LANDIS, E. J. KUHAJEK, P. E. R. NORDQUIST and L. MAYER, in S. KIRSCHNER (Ed.), "Coordination Chemistry, Proc. JOHN C. BAILAR, Jr. Symp.," Plenum Press, New York, 1969; J. S. MADARAS and H. G. BRITAIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 38; *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 42, 109, 198; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, 20, 959, 3007, 4267, 4273.
9. S. KIRSCHNER and K. R. MAGNELL, in "Werner Centennial" Advances in Chemistry, Series No. 62, American Chemical Society, Washington, D.C., 1966, p. 366 ff.
10. K. MIYOSHI, Y. KURODA, J. TAKEDA, H. YONEDA and I. TAKAGI, in press; K. MIYOSHI, K. SAKATA and H. YONEDA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1976, 80, 6 9; 1975, 79, 1622; K. MIYOSHI, Y. KURODA and H. YONEDA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1976, 80, 270, 649; H. YONEDA et al, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, 31, L453; 1978, 28, 211; *Chem. Lett. (J.)*, 1978, 763.
11. S. KIRSCHNER, R. MORASKI, C. MUNIR, N. AHMAD and R. POLLOCK, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1977, 22, 1283.
12. P. E. SCHIPPER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 12, 199.
13. S. KIRSCHNER and N. AHMAD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 1910.
14. S. KIRSCHNER and N. AHMAD, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 14, 215.
15. S. KIRSCHNER, N. AHMAD, C. MUNIR and R. POLLOCK, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1979, 51, 913.
16. S. KIRSCHNER and P. SERDIUK, in B. DOUGLAS and Y. SAITO (Eds.), "Stereochemistry of Optically Active Transition Metal Compounds", American Chemical Society, Washington, D. C., 1980, p. 239 ff.
17. H. IWAMURA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, 2227; Z. YOSHIDA and E. O. OSAWA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 4019.
18. P. J. KRUEGER and H. D. METTE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, 1587; M. OKO and H. IWANORA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 576.
19. R. S. CAHN and C. K. INGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 612.
20. R. S. CAHN, C. K. INGOLD and V. PRELOG, *Experientia*, 1956, 12, 81.
21. G. B. KAUFFMAN and L. T. TAKAHASHI, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1966, 8, 227.